

Application of coal fly ash, cow dung and grass cuttings mix in cultivation of few vegetables of *Solanaceae* family

Krishna Rani and Kalpana S.*

P.G. Department of Chemistry, Govt. College, Kota-324 001, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : kr10360@gmail.com

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Abstract : Addition of coal fly ash (CFA), a by-product of Thermal Power Plants, with soil alters its physical and chemical properties. Few pot and field experiments were conducted to study the impact of bio modified CFA in cultivation of selected varieties of tomato and brinjal/egg plant fruit and physicochemical studies have been carried out for different composts obtained by successive replacement of CFA for soil/earth in constituents of original or reference compost. Cow dung and grass cuttings were used as organic manure. CFA obtained from Kota Super Thermal Power Plant was used. Increase in rate of growth and improvement in quality of product was observed with the increase in percentage of CFA.

Keywords : Coal fly ash, compost, Kota Super Thermal Power Plant, bio modified.

Introduction

Sustainable management of large volumes of CFA of Thermal Power Plants poses a big challenge for a country like India. Researchers have been attempting to convert this waste into wealth by exploring viable avenues. The chemical and physical properties of CFA are determined by several variables such as coal source, degree of pulverization, design of boiler unit, loading and firing conditions, handling and storage methods¹.

Researches till date show that addition of fly ash may change the chemical as well as physical properties of soil which in turn determine the biological properties irrespective of the crop²⁻⁸ and the CFA worked as soil modifier and nutrients supplier in cultivation of number of crops⁹⁻¹³. Therefore in order to enhance percent utilization and to generate acceptability towards waste materials CFA and organic wastes in cultivation of few vegetables such as brinjal (*Solanum melongena*) and tomato (*Solanum*

or *Lycopersicum esculentum*) were chosen and the study aimed to determine the effect of graded levels of CFA on physicochemical properties of soil. Cow dung and grass cuttings were used as organic manure.

Today India is the second largest producer of fruits (≈ 44 million tones/annum) and vegetables (≈ 87.5 million tones/annum). Production share of major Solanaceous vegetables brinjal, tomato and chilli in India is about 25% of total production. The Solanaceous fruits when immature are green and change colour on ripening. The fruits are fried, baked, cooked with meat, made into soup, sauce and salad.

Materials and methods :

Himsoma, round shaped desi type (Registered seeds from Sygenta Seed Limited) variety of tomato and Pusa Kranti, a high yielding variety of brinjal suitable for growing round the year have been chosen for the study.

Table 1. Constituents of reference compost and other parameters

	Tomato	Brinjal
Amount of seeds	150 g/hectare	300 g/hectare
Amount of urea	100 kg/hectare (50% at the time of planting and 50% after 4 weeks)	100 kg/hectare (50% at the time of planting and 50% after 2.5 weeks)
Constitution of reference compost	3 part (clay and sand) + 1 part of grass cuttings + 1 part of cow dung manure	3 parts of clay + 1 part of grass cuttings + 1 part of cow dung manure
Time chosen for cultivation	March/April of every year 2005, 2006 and 2007	March/April of every year 2005, 2006 and 2007

For pot experiments CFA samples were collected arbitrarily following the standard technique quarter and cone. Samples were air dried and stored at room temperature before mixing it for converting into composts. As an organic manure cow dung and grass cuttings were mixed. Different composition of composts were prepared by gradual replacement of soil by CFA (from 10% to 50%) in reference compost. For conversion into composts left these admixtures in separate damp pits (\approx 4 feet in depth) for about 1.5 month. After 1.5 month, ten pots were prepared for each composition of compost. Density, texture, water holding capacity and porosity were determined by adopting standard techniques for soil analysis and pH potentiometrically^{14,15}.

Chemical analysis for nitrate, phosphate, sulphate, potassium, calcium, manganese, magnesium, copper, zinc and iron have been carried out following standard chemical analysis method^{14,15}. A.R. grade chemicals were used for analysis.

Radioactivity tests obtained from ESL, Nuclear Power Corporation, Rawatbhata for ²³²Th, ²³⁸U and ⁴⁰K elements in a sample of CFA used for the purpose were within limits not hazardous to human health. Toxic heavy metal analysis for compost giving best results of produce and product obtained was carried out and the results showed that uptake of heavy metals was within permissible range.

Experiments for study of plant growth and quality and yield of produce were carried out in pots. Seeds were sown in reference composts and seedlings were transplanted in the pots of identical dimensions packed with composts of different constitution after reaching definite height (15 cm). Chosen varieties of brinjal and tomato were grown according to their requirements of water, support and climatic conditions as referred in standard agriculture literature¹⁶⁻¹⁹. The plants were allowed to grow till maturity and then harvested. The food samples were thoroughly washed, dried and powdered for analysis. Observations regarding pests and disease attack were recorded time to time.

To find out utility of composts preparation, simultaneous experiments were conducted under similar conditions by growing chosen vegetables directly in similar mixtures of soil, CFA, cow dung and grass cuttings.

Similar pot experiments were carried out in three consecutive years 2005, 2006 and 2007. In 2007 field experiments were also carried out in one hectare area for each vegetable.

Results and discussion

Physicochemical properties of CFA depend on their origin and the composition of coal used for combustion. The preparation of different composts by application of different % of CFA resulted in favourable bio physicochemical changes with modification of soil properties with an increase in available nutrients (N, P, K, Ca, Mg, S,

Table 2. Physical properties of different composts prepared with CFA for tomato (T) and brinjal/egg plant fruit (B)

Parameters→		Texture	Organic matter (%)	Water holding capacity (%)	Porosity (%)	Density (g cm ⁻³)	pH	Conductivity (μ mho cm ⁻¹)
Compost	For							
C ₀	T	Sandy clay	0.725	41.50	41.65	1.280	5.80	114.0
	B	clay	0.875	62.50	52.30	1.260	5.60	140.0
C ₁	T	Sandy clay	0.705	42.00	43.05	1.245	5.95	118.5
	B	Silty clay	0.850	62.00	53.08	1.180	5.80	134.0
C ₂	T	Clay	0.685	42.65	44.50	1.210	6.10	122.5
	B	Loam	0.820	61.50	54.00	1.130	6.05	142.0
C ₃	T	Loamy clay	0.670	43.50	46.70	1.180	6.30	130.0
	B	Loam	0.805	61.00	54.40	1.100	6.30	148.0
C ₄	T	Loamy clay	0.650	44.75	49.30	1.155	6.20	134.0
	B	Loam	0.780	61.00	55.60	1.080	6.10	153.0
C ₅	T	Loamy clay	0.633	45.50	47.30	1.160	6.05	144.5
	B	Loam	0.757	60.00	54.60	1.090	5.90	158.0

Table 3. Primary and secondary nutrients in different composts prepared with CFA for tomato (T) and brinjal/egg plant fruit (B) in %

Nutrients→		Primary			Secondary		
Compost	For	NO ₃ ⁻	PO ₄ ³⁻	K ⁺	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	SO ₄ ²⁻
↓	↓						
C ₀	T	0.0105	0.0050	0.0800	0.40	0.22	0.030
	B	0.0019	0.0054	0.0069	0.84	0.59	0.100
C ₁	T	0.0100	0.0060	0.0850	0.42	0.23	0.040
	B	0.0024	0.0064	0.0094	0.84	0.30	0.110
C ₂	T	0.0095	0.0060	0.0800	0.52	0.21	0.035
	B	0.0019	0.0064	0.0104	0.93	0.40	0.110
C ₃	T	0.0510	0.0062	0.0820	0.60	0.24	0.005
	B	0.0024	0.0079	0.0104	0.95	0.54	0.120
C ₄	T	0.0500	0.0064	0.0820	0.62	0.39	0.005
	B	0.0024	0.0059	0.0104	0.99	0.75	0.120
C ₅	T	0.0460	0.0065	0.0750	0.52	0.41	0.005
	B	0.0021	0.0064	0.0094	1.01	0.81	0.120

Table 4. Micro nutrients in different composts prepared with CFA for tomato (T) and brinjal/egg plant fruit (B) in ppm

Nutrients→		Cu	Zn	Fe	Mn
Compost	For				
↓	↓				
C ₀	T	0.6	0.70	3.8	1.10
	B	1.3	1.40	6.5	1.30
C ₁	T	0.7	0.72	3.7	0.40
	B	1.4	1.42	6.4	0.60
C ₂	T	0.9	0.50	3.7	0.44
	B	1.7	1.20	6.5	0.60
C ₃	T	1.0	0.60	4.5	0.60
	B	1.8	1.20	7.3	0.70
C ₄	T	1.1	1.00	5.7	0.70
	B	1.9	1.80	8.1	0.70
C ₅	T	1.1	1.10	6.0	0.50
	B	1.9	2.00	8.7	0.70

Table 5. Heavy metal analysis of the tomato and brinjal obtained from compost giving best results in ppm

Heavy metal	Tomato	Brinjal
Cu	10.78	8.92
Zn	25.20	207.77
Cd	0.10	0.01
Pb	12.17	2.25
Fe	96.27	138.00
B	10.72	8.67

Fe, Mn, Zn and Cu). With chosen varieties of vegetables, an improvement in fertility is observed up to 40% replacement of soil by CFA.

(i) *Physical parameters :*

Table 2 contains results obtained for density, porosity and water holding capacity determined for different composts prepared for studies. As the composition of the mixture or compost changes from 1 to 5, the porosity increases and density decreases with the increase in percentage of CFA in reference compost (C₁ to C₄) while in C₅ the trend has got reversed. In case of reference compost used for tomato water holding capacity increases and in case of reference compost used for brinjal water holding capacity decreases with the increase in percentage of CFA.

Table 2 also shows pH changes with the increase in percentage of CFA in compost mixture. At first an increase is observed (from C₁ to C₃) after reaching an optimum value the trend has got reversed (from C₃ to C₄ and C₅). It may be due to the increase in salt content like calcium oxide (CaO) and magnesium oxide (MgO) and their dissociation possibilities contributed from the alkaline CFA added. The electrical conductivity was increased due to the increasing quantity of soluble macro and micro nutrients (Tables 3 and 4) released by the added CFA or by the interaction of inorganic constituents of CFA with soil organic matter.

(ii) *Available plant nutrients in composts prepared with CFA :*

With the increase in dose of CFA the availability of most of the macronutrients is found to increase up to

certain ratio. The release of the nutrients in the ionic form increasing their bioavailability which can be considered favourable results of chain of chemical reactions among constituents of composts at more suitable pH and physical conditions i.e. better texture, reduced density, increased porosity with appropriate water holding capacity. This helps in increasing the concentration of nutrients and conditions of the soil medium to assimilate the nutrients by plants following specific physiological mechanism.

The available nitrogen was measured in terms of NO_3^- . The available phosphorous was measured in terms of phosphate. The increase in concentration of phosphate may be attributed to the available phosphorus present in CFA. Plants take phosphate in HPO_4^{2-} form. The increase is due to the hydrolysis of iron, aluminum and magnesium compounds in CFA and released inorganic acids by CFA. The liberated acids help in the release of available phosphate from the unavailable form without affecting the pH as organic matter present in the soil has a buffering capacity in maintaining the pH.

Potassium was measured in terms of K^+ in soil and CFA. In CFA, it is present in the form of complex constituents, albite and mizzonite which probably after several transformations release ions in the similar form contributing to the soil. The availability of K^+ ion is low at higher dose of CFA due to low percentage of clay and cation exchange capacity. Calcium and magnesium in soil and CFA are present in the form of silicates and oxides. The availability of calcium and magnesium increases on increase in % of CFA.

Sulphur is taken up by plants in SO_4^{2-} form. At very higher level of CFA C_4 and C_5 , the decrease in the SO_4^{2-} may be pertained due to the combined (imbalance) effect of clay, silt and sand content, microbial activity, organic matter and pH. It is reported by some researchers that at higher concentration of CFA some heavy metals become more active and hinder the microbial activity. pH plays a vital role in the release of specific nutrients. The availability of nutrients is maximum at 5.5 to 6.5 pH.

During present studies no symptoms of chlorosis were observed even though presence of zinc and copper was in higher limit in soil CFA mixtures. This may be due to the physicochemical properties of CFA which on mixing with soil has ameliorated the soil from sandy clay to loamy clay in case of tomato and clay to loam in case of brinjal and due to the presence of oxides of calcium and magnesium which maintained alkalinity.

Table 4 indicates that copper is increased with the increase in concentration of CFA but did not impart any toxicity as excess availability was hindered due to alkaline pH, organic matter and clay content. In CFA copper is present in form of tenorite (CuO) which helps in the release of available copper. Present studies clearly reveal that CFA worked as soil modifier and nutrients supplier in cultivation of brinjal and tomato. Results indicate that CFA improved physical and morphological properties of soil, water retention capacity of soil together with increased release of nutrient elements such as calcium, magnesium, sulphur, potassium, copper, phosphorous, zinc etc. Best results in terms of plant growth, maturation period, quality and quantity of produce were obtained with composts containing 40% (v/v) of CFA of total volume. Yield of tomato and brinjal was maximum in case of compost having 40% CFA v/v. Maximum percentage increase in yield of tomato and brinjal was 33.66% and 51.04% respectively in comparison to reference compost. It was found that heavy metals uptake was within permissible limits. Table 5 shows the heavy metal analysis of tomato and brinjal obtained from compost giving best results.

The plants and the edible part of vegetables were observed ten times less prone to pest, fruit borer and six times less prone to disease leaf curl. From simultaneous experiments carried out in unmodified mixture of CFA, cow dung and grass cuttings, under similar conditions, the obtained edible part of vegetables was comparatively poor by quality according to food standards.

Conclusion :

The results obtained in field experiments, quality and quantity wise, were quite encouraging for both the vegetables. Therefore, CFA can be applied (dose 40% v/v) advantageously in cultivation of vegetables (brinjal and tomato) of family *Solanaceae*. Constant amount of grass cuttings and cow dung has helped in increasing potassium, calcium, phosphorous and organic carbon in the mixture.

Utilization of CFA, grass cuttings and cow dung in proper amount and proper way can act as boon in agriculture sector giving solution to safe and sustainable management of these wastes which also act as soil saver and irrigation water saver. Long term studies are under progress.

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